

Integrating ATR Software with University HPC Infrastructure: balancing diverse compute needs

Christine Roughan
Center for Digital Humanities
Princeton University
Princeton, NJ, USA

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5999-8749>

Rebecca Sutton Koeser
Center for Digital Humanities
Princeton University
Princeton, NJ, USA

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8762-8057>

Abstract—There is increasing interest in automated text recognition (ATR) tools from faculty and students in the humanities and social sciences, as well as from university library professionals. Further, there is interest in the ability to train or fine-tune such machine learning models because out-of-the-box tools often return subpar results for historical or otherwise low-resource languages. In this paper, we report on our contributions to the implementation of an open-source ATR platform (eScriptorium) on university hardware and in a Slurm-managed high-performance computing (HPC) environment. We comment on modifications required for deployment, authentication, and HPC integration, as well as on decisions made regarding code modularity and strategies to handle the diverse runtime and compute requirements of user-submitted model training tasks.

Index Terms—universities, research software engineering, text recognition, high performance computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

There is increasing interest in the application of automated text recognition (ATR) tools to printed and handwritten materials from scholars in the humanities and social sciences, as well as from professionals in libraries, archives, and other cultural heritage institutions. In recent years a variety of tools have been developed to handle this task – among these, see Calfa Vision [1], eScriptorium / kraken [2], [3], OCR4all [4], [5], Transkribus [6]–[8], and tranSkriptorium [9], [10], not to mention custom-designed tools (e.g. [11]). Even with the recent rise of multimodal LLMs and powerful tools such as Google Vision API [12], university researchers are often unable to find an out-of-the-box recognition model with highly accurate results for their material: these tools still return poorer results for historical and/or low-resource languages, as well as for pages with complex or otherwise unusual layouts. In the university we have therefore seen particular interest in software that provides the user with the ability to finetune or create their own models.

These training tasks are machine learning ones and are compute-intensive, requiring access to GPUs to run in a timely and efficient manner. At Princeton University, institutional

compute resources are available through the High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters managed by the university’s Research Computing unit. This past year, a research infrastructure project (“The Princeton Open HTR Initiative”) funded by a seed grant from Princeton Language and Intelligence (PLI) and led by Marina Rustow, Helmut Reimitz, and Christine Roughan set out to create institutional infrastructure to support ATR usage by campus community members. The project engaged in a Research Partnership with Princeton’s Center for Digital Humanities (CDH) for the purpose of adapting an existing ATR solution to function in the university hardware context. In this collaboration, lead RSE Rebecca Sutton Koeser and project manager Christine Roughan adapted the open source eScriptorium platform to function using institutional HPC hardware and according to university requirements.

Our goal with this project was to separate out the computing needs and make use of campus infrastructure so that provisioning and supporting a university-wide instance of eScriptorium would not require investment in substantial new hardware (with associated administrative and maintenance costs), but would instead make use of existing HPC resources managed by Princeton’s Research Computing unit.

B. Background

1) *On eScriptorium*: The ATR platform we selected was eScriptorium, an open-source web application that allows for free importing and exporting of both data and trained models, whether for image segmentation or text transcription tasks [13]. It provides users with an editing environment along with a GUI capable of running and training models using the kraken ATR engine (otherwise available via the command line and as a Python library) [14]. Our choice of eScriptorium for this project was motivated by:

- available functionality: it enables users to run existing models but also, more importantly, to train their own; this includes the ability to finetune pre-existing models;
- multi-user support: while it is possible to install eScriptorium on a personal computer for individual use, the platform is designed for multiple user accounts and also includes team functionality to support sharing projects, data, and models across those accounts;

This work was supported by the Princeton Language and Intelligence (PLI) Seed Grant Program and by a Collaborative Research Grant from the Princeton Center for Digital Humanities.

- data handling: users are free to import and export both training data and trained models, allowing for users (a) to take advantage of previously published and shared data and models from sources like Zenodo and HTR-United [15], and (b) to export their own data and models to share or publish in whichever venues they desire;
- data security: by installing and running the software locally, data never leaves institutional hardware and networks, which is important when working with copyrighted or otherwise sensitive images; and
- use of open-source software: because eScriptorium’s code is available for review, we were able to determine what modifications would be necessary for it to function in our specific institutional context.

2) *On Princeton HPC Clusters:* As of 2025, Princeton’s Research Computing unit manages seven HPC clusters of varying specifications. Among these are clusters that specifically provide GPU nodes, which are crucial for training and fine-tuning models. Research Computing makes these resources available to the university community, though certain clusters require specific approval to access. The minimum requirement for access to a cluster with GPU nodes is submission of a form to request access; more powerful clusters require a faculty sponsor and project approval. Access requires university credentials and connection either to the university network or VPN.

The clusters which we were targeting for our project all have the additional constraint that job submission is managed by a Slurm scheduling system [16]. This was a key challenge that our institutional installation of eScriptorium would have to navigate: while other eScriptorium instances have been established in HPC environments (including the flagship Paris instance of eScriptorium, manuscriptologia or msIA, currently hosted at the Paris Observatory), the software had not been designed to function in a Slurm-managed environment.

II. DEPLOYMENT AND ACCESS

A. Application Deployment

While eScriptorium is usually installed on a powerful computer to handle running the relevant machine learning tasks – its GitLab wiki does in fact recommend a HPC cluster – the application actually has a mix of computing needs. The web application provides a user interface for managing data (users, images, transcriptions, models), running recognition tasks (segmentation and transcription), and training new models. Some of those tasks are more demanding than others, but only the model training tasks require GPUs.

The software provides two documented methods for deployment. There are step-by-step instructions to set up a local install, which is primarily intended for setting up a development instance for project contributors. A Docker install is also available.

After reviewing existing deployment options and typical components needed to run eScriptorium, we decided to deploy the application in a manner that is as similar as possible to

other Python/Django web applications developed at CDH. As a small research unit, CDH does not have any systems support or server infrastructure of our own, but we have a longstanding agreement with Princeton University Library (PUL) to provide virtual machines and lightweight operations support. Following our standard practices, we requested two virtual machines (VMs) which would be run in parallel for redundancy, and storage space for images uploaded for transcription, using network file system (NFS) so it could be made available on both machines. We then wrote an Ansible playbook for an automated, replicable deploy of eScriptorium, borrowing as much as possible from other CDH Ansible playbooks. The playbook installs necessary system packages, checks out a copy of the eScriptorium software and installs Python and npm dependencies, configures the main web application to run with the nginx web server with passenger, and installs and configures supervisor to manage two ancillary processes: Django Channels, for asynchronous communication and messages, and Celery, a task queuing system for long-running processes.

We made an effort to keep our installation for this project consistent with existing Python/Django applications developed at CDH. Like those applications, our setup takes advantage of services and infrastructure that are centrally managed by PUL IT Operations; these include a Postgresql server for the application database, a mail relay system for application email messages, as well as a load balancer which proxies public requests to the actual VMs. PUL also runs a centralized Redis service, but our PUL collaborators advised us to start with a local Redis instance at first (some PUL applications are also configured this way), and only change if it caused problems. Additionally, since this was a test instance and our beta test was intended for Princeton community members only, our VMs were provisioned in a private library subnet; these machines are not publicly accessible and could only be used on Princeton campus or Princeton VPN, which provides an extra layer of security. (This was helpful, since we did not have to wait for the rigorous security review applied to external software tools which are being considered for publicly accessible services.) Our setup is a contrast to the Docker deploy documented for eScriptorium, which provides a comprehensive set of Docker hosts for every related service (e.g. database, redis, email server) and which would not have suited our ecosystem.

We intentionally started with minimal, underpowered VMs (2 CPUs and 16 GB of memory) because we wanted to determine how well eScriptorium worked with limited hardware. We scaled up both CPUs and memory during our own internal testing and finally requested one more increase in anticipation of the beta test we would run of the software. For the beta test, the VMs were equipped with 8 CPUs and 64 GB of memory to better support the added users and the increase in concurrent jobs, especially recognition jobs. Using an Ansible playbook also made it possible to adjust certain configurations dynamically, such as the number of Celery queues and workers.

B. Authentication

Once we had a functional eScriptorium installation with an automated deploy mechanism through our Ansible playbook, our first customization was for authentication. eScriptorium uses a standard Django user account which stores encrypted passwords in the application database. On top of this, eScriptorium adds administrative functionality and email messages for inviting users to join the application (which makes sense for its original multi-institution, multi-project context). In our case, it was important to integrate with Princeton’s Single Sign-On (SSO), which is based on Central Authentication Service (CAS). Fortunately, since other CDH applications have been written in Python/Django and needed the same CAS integration, we had an existing Python library (`django-pucas` [17]) that could be dropped in as a dependency with a known working configuration, and a custom management script for provisioning new accounts with varying permissions.

University CAS integration was desirable for multiple reasons. It is a helpful security measure, since it restricts access to campus community members; using SSO meant that we would not have to store passwords in the application database. But it was also crucial that the accounts for our instance of eScriptorium be based on Princeton credentials, since that was a requirement for HPC integration at Princeton: Research Computing only allows jobs to be submitted by university user accounts.

III. HPC INTEGRATION

Once we had a working installation of eScriptorium with SSO authentication that could handle low- and medium-compute tasks, our next phase of work was the heart of this project: integration with Princeton HPC resources. Before diving into implementation, we spent some time reviewing related resources and talking to campus contacts about options for HPC integration at Princeton.

A. Existing solutions

We were aware of one eScriptorium instance which had been installed to function in a similar Slurm-managed HPC context — although the university’s Scientific Computing Support team had already communicated they did not think their solution was generalizable. This is the “FoNDUE” instance (FoRmes Numerisees et Detection Unifree des Ecritures) at the University of Geneva in Switzerland [18]. Fortunately, the software for their solution is publicly available as open source, which enabled us to review and assess their approach as we formulated our own. The FoNDUE instance of eScriptorium is powered by a custom fork of the software [19] paired with a custom REST API for Slurm, Slurmer [20]. Because this project is forked from the main eScriptorium code, we were able to review changes and could see two different approaches to the problem of modifying eScriptorium to submit Slurm jobs: a first approach based on SSH access, and a second solution using the Slurmer API. Their integration comprises a number of changes, including custom database models to track and monitor jobs on the cluster, changes to the web UI

to integrate cluster job information, and replacing the built in training tasks with replacements that implemented remote task management using the Slurmer API.

We had not expected to be able to use the FoNDUE solution directly for a few reasons, and a closer review of the Slurmer application confirmed our suspicions. This application must be run on an HPC cluster head node and with external access to the REST API. It additionally needs a mechanism for running tasks as other users, which Princeton Research Computing was closed to as a potential security risk. However, reviewing their approach was enlightening and helpful in forming our own strategy. Among other things, we learned that there is an existing REST API for Slurm [21]. Upon further investigation, we found that the official Slurm REST API was not enabled on Princeton HPCs, and that there were neither plans nor interest in setting it up. It was also through reading the Slurmer report that we became aware that many Slurm command-line utilities have an option for JSON output.

During our investigation phase, we also became aware of Globus Compute [22] and the related underlying Python library `parsl` [23], both of which offer solutions for remote computation with support for a variety of systems and architectures. We did not pursue Globus Compute for this project because it offered a more heavyweight solution than what was necessary for our present needs, although it may be of interest for future work. We experimented with `parsl`, but ultimately it was not a good fit for our use case. It is intended for much larger, repeatable data workflows, and while it does provide support for Slurm because it is intended to work across many different systems, it was difficult to customize the Slurm jobs to our needs.

B. APIs and SSH

The approach we ultimately implemented leverages the eScriptorium REST APIs for access from the HPC system and uses SSH for task management from the eScriptorium VM. We have packaged the full code for our approach in a Python application, `htr2hpc` [24], and we will discuss this choice further in section IV.

We first wrote a Python script that accomplished the following:

- 1) download training content and optionally a preliminary model from eScriptorium,
- 2) start and monitor a training job via Slurm command line tools (`sbatch` and `squeue`), and
- 3) upload the resulting model to eScriptorium.

We initially implemented this as a standalone script which could be installed and run on the cluster without integration into the eScriptorium web UI or task queuing system. This was of immediate use for testing out our workflows.

eScriptorium REST APIs are implemented with Django REST Framework and provide robust access to all the important kinds of content in the system: documents, parts of documents (pages), transcriptions, segmentation, models, etc. There is also an existing third-party Python API client, `escriptorium-connector` [25]. Unfortunately,

we quickly discovered that the third-party client works around a strange limitation of the eScriptorium APIs by requiring *both* an API token and user credentials in order to monitor asynchronous messages sent via the web interface that provide information not available in the API. Storing and passing Princeton SSO account credentials for use in this script made this unacceptable for our context.

Fig. 1. Architecture diagram of the deployment of the Princeton eScriptorium instance, with remote task functionality supported by the HPC integration. For simplicity, we omit the load balancer and second VM from this architecture diagram. Both instances of eScriptorium are deployed as diagrammed, and use the same shared PUL and HPC infrastructure.

Fortunately, we were able to quickly build out Python API client code for the endpoints we needed to use for retrieving document image, region, and transcription content and for retrieving and uploading models. In the end, our custom client code gave us important flexibility. Rather than relying on an existing eScriptorium download task, which provides a packaged download of all the requested components, we wrote code to consume specific API content and convert it to the appropriate format for the requested training task.

Once we had implemented and tested the command-line training script, we worked to integrate into the eScriptorium web application. We replaced the existing Celery training tasks with custom versions that use the Python library *fabric* [26] to create a secure shell (SSH) connection to the HPC head node as the currently logged in user and run the training script as that user. Our custom task updates statuses appropriately within eScriptorium, including updating model status to indicate when it is being trained; we also send script output and logging information to the task reports in the database – this greatly facilitated troubleshooting in testing and development phases. For convenience, we provide the user with a link to the OnDemand [27] web interface for the HPC cluster, which allows them to monitor the status of the training job in Slurm.

Running the job remotely via SSH was the approach recommended by Research Computing staff for this project, as it was a known working solution that had been used for other projects with similar needs. We use key-based authentication; eScriptorium users who want this functionality are required to install an SSH key on their account on the HPC head node, and are informed what this allows. Additionally, we requested and received an exemption from the standard two-factor authentication for SSH access from the eScriptorium VMs to the HPC head node – this was another case where we benefited from adapting a known solution that had been used for other projects.

One option we considered but did not have time to prototype was a custom OnDemand application, which could provide similar functionality but preserve a consistent web interface throughout the process and simplify authentication. This would have been a simple Python Flask application with documented URL patterns for triggering the specified tasks. If this application were set up with Single Sign-on, then logging in and accessing the cluster with an individual account would be seamless.

C. Automating one-time user environment setup

Running the training tasks on the HPC systems does require some initial setup for each user who wants to use the functionality. This involves adding the public SSH key for access from the eScriptorium VMs and provisioning a Python environment with all the dependencies installed. Our first step to streamline this process was a bash script that would automate the process. But since many of the users in our target audience for this application are not particularly technical, we decided to further smooth the process by adding a custom Celery task in eScriptorium to run the setup which could be triggered by a button from the user’s profile page. This meant that the only step which required the user to interact with the command line was the step to add the SSH public key for remote access. We therefore set up each user’s profile page to provide them with the one-line command needed to activate the SSH key.

D. Maintenance

During our beta testing period, the HPC system went through an upgrade from RedHat 8 to RedHat 9. This timing might seem unfortunate, but in fact it was a valuable experience to get a sense of what long-term maintenance of this integration might look like in practice. In this case, the maintenance was relatively painless: we tested that the training script worked on the new version, requested the two-factor authentication exemption for the new head node, and updated the application configuration to update the remote server name for running the remote training task. This occurred during a downtime period for the software and so the redeployment did not interrupt ongoing user tasks.

In addition, we anticipated that future upgrades might require updates to the Python environments that each user had initialized during their account setup. We therefore added in functionality that would allow users to press a button in their eScriptorium account to update their copies of these environments when needed.

IV. MODULARITY OF CODE

One of our priorities while integrating eScriptorium with our Slurm-managed HPC environment was developing a lightweight approach that would not require significant additional maintenance work. We therefore avoided forking the eScriptorium code, since that approach would have required more maintenance in the long run should any significant patches be made to the main branch (addressing important security risks or other concerns, for instance). Since the project continues to enjoy active development from multiple different institutions and projects, we knew this would be a moving target; in fact, even in the version of the software used for our instance (dev-0.14.2) there are two different user interfaces available.

Our solution was to package our contributions as a companion Python application, `htr2hpc`, which can be used independently for training via eScriptorium APIs and which also provides optional configuration and Celery tasks for integration with the Django application [24]. Although eScriptorium is currently set up as a standalone application rather than a Django module or set of modules that could be used in other applications, it is still possible to include additional Django modules in the configured list of installed applications. In addition, we used Ansible capabilities for modifying files to patch the installed eScriptorium code in order to replace the default training tasks with the custom tasks in our package and to adjust one template for a one-line change that was not easily handled by extending the template.

This last set of changes is admittedly somewhat brittle, and would need monitoring and testing against new versions of eScriptorium. However, if our approach is pursued for further adoption, we would advocate for and potentially help contribute improvements to the main eScriptorium codebase to make these kinds of interventions configurable without patching.

V. HANDLING DIVERSE COMPUTE NEEDS

A. The Problem

One of the key challenges in integrating ATR software into institutional compute resources was how to address the widely-ranging time and compute requirements for different tasks.

On a macro level this involved determining what categories of jobs would be handled on the VMs hosting the software versus which ones would be redirected to the HPC cluster. This was the more straightforward question to answer: only tasks training new segmentation or text transcription models required access to GPU resources in order to run effectively. As section III-B discusses, our code contributions redirect these tasks to the HPC cluster while tasks such as model inference, data editing and management, etc. are handled on the virtual machines.

The situation for determining runtime and compute requirements for each individual train job a user might run was more complicated. When the software sent these train tasks to the HPC cluster, it sent them to an environment where such compute-heavy tasks needed to be submitted through a Slurm job scheduling system. It was therefore necessary to specify parameters including requested runtime, number of tasks, CPUs per task, and memory per CPU as part of that job submission.

This posed a challenge in our work because the train tasks the software was to support are not equal in either their runtime or compute requirements. A task training a segmentation model on 500 images of training data would use significantly more resources than one doing so on 50 images. Model refining an existing text transcription model for Latin manuscripts on pages from a new but similar Latin manuscript would converge much faster than refining on that same model to jumpstart a new text recognition model for Greek manuscripts. The challenge was therefore twofold.

- 1) Larger sets of training data (more images or greater file sizes) or more complicated sets (greater numbers of categories to classify) increased both the duration and CPU needs of each epoch.
- 2) The model training process runs through multiple epochs until the model converges, and while one model might take ten epochs to converge, another might not do so until the fiftieth epoch.

Our anticipated audience of students, scholars, and cultural heritage professionals would bring in widely-varying data and running training jobs with diverse requirements. We sought to provide software that could handle these needs and dynamically adjust the requested resources in the Slurm submissions as needed.

B. Scaling Analysis

To gain a clearer picture of how runtime and compute requirements changed with different parameters of the input training data, we ran a series of abbreviated test training jobs on different training data sets. For the data used for this scaling

analysis we took advantage of an open source dataset (the e-NDP project [28]) which provided 512 segmented pages and transcriptions. We normalized this data so that all images were of nearly equal filesize (approximately 612.7 KB) and then ran batches of tests comparing the resources needed to train segmentation and transcription models on 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, and 500 images, respectively.

Each training task was aborted after five epochs: this provided data for both initialization and average epoch runtimes (CPU usage and epoch duration otherwise does not change significantly between different epochs in the same training run). Results can be seen in Tables I, II, III, and IV.

TABLE I
TRAINING A SEGMENTATION MODEL FROM SCRATCH

Training data image count	Runtime for five epochs	Time increase / image increase	Max CPU usage	Max GPU uage
10	0:02:07	1.00	13.7 GB	4.4 GiB
20	0:03:13	0.76	17.1 GB	4.4 GiB
50	0:04:37	0.44	23.8 GB	5.2 GiB
100	0:09:33	0.45	38.4 GB	6.9 GiB
200	0:15:17	0.36	35.6 GB	7.4 GiB
500	0:37:31	0.35	43.1 GB	8.3 GiB

TABLE II
REFINING A SEGMENTATION MODEL ON ANOTHER MODEL

Training data image count	Runtime for five epochs	Time increase / image increase	Max CPU usage	Max GPU uage
10	0:01:47	1.00	10.7 GB	4.4 GiB
20	0:02:18	0.64	15.8 GB	4.4 GiB
50	0:04:21	0.49	20.8 GB	5.1 GiB
100	0:10:32	0.59	35.4 GB	6.6 GiB
200	0:14:54	0.42	36.0 GB	7.4 GiB
500	0:38:12	0.43	49.3 GB	7.7 GiB

TABLE III
TRAINING A TRANSCRIPTION MODEL FROM SCRATCH

Training data image count	Runtime for five epochs	Time increase / image increase	Max CPU usage	Max GPU uage
10	0:02:46	1.00	3.9 GB	2.3 GiB
20	0:03:28	0.63	4.6 GB	2.3 GiB
50	0:07:27	0.54	5.0 GB	2.3 GiB
100	0:16:02	0.58	5.9 GB	2.8 GiB
200	0:32:53	0.59	6.8 GB	2.8 GiB
500	1:23:17	0.60	7.8 GB	2.5 GiB

These tests also measured the impact of training from scratch versus refining on an existing model, and of changing the amount of data to classify per image (number of regions for segmentation, number of characters for transcription). See for example Table V.

C. Solution: a two-job workflow

Upon evaluation of the test results, we settled on step functions for the two types of train jobs (segmentation and

TABLE IV
REFINING A TRANSCRIPTION MODEL ON ANOTHER MODEL

Training data image count	Runtime for five epochs	Time increase / image increase	Max CPU usage	Max GPU uage
10	0:03:05	1.00	5.7 GB	1.5 GiB
20	0:03:20	0.54	6.3 GB	1.5 GiB
50	0:07:26	0.48	7.0 GB	1.5 GiB
100	0:15:12	0.49	8.0 GB	1.6 GiB
200	0:29:45	0.48	8.9 GB	1.6 GiB
500	1:15:44	0.49	8.8 GB	1.6 GiB

TABLE V
IMPACT OF LINE LENGTH ON EPOCH TIMES

Training data image count	Training data line count	Line length	Average epoch duration
500	7538	less than 11 characters	113.4 seconds
500	7537	greater than 67 characters	361.8 seconds

transcription) that would approximate the required resources for a given total training data filesize. These functions erred towards over-requesting resources so that jobs would not fail prematurely.

Since the above approach did overestimate resource requirements, however, and since large training jobs could potentially claim many cluster hours, we developed an the below approach that would more precisely calibrate the runtime and compute resource requests to be submitted to Slurm for a given training job. This calibrated approach greatly improved the efficiency of requested resource usage, which was of course a benefit both in more responsible cluster usage and ensuring users' cluster accounts were not automatically penalized with longer queue times for inefficient requests.

Our final approach was a two-job workflow that would run two Slurm jobs for each submitted train task – the first job a shorter one, run for the purpose of calibrating the requirements to be submitted for the second job.

The parameters of this first job are calculated with the step functions noted above – however, we cap the runtime of this first job at a maximum of fifteen minutes. After its completion, our code queries its actual resource usage using the `jobstats` command (available through the open source Jobstats platform [29]), parses the output, and uses that data to determine the appropriate runtime, CPU count, and CPU memory needed for the second train task.

This second train task submitted to Slurm is the one intended to complete the training in full. Calculating the required CPU count and memory is straightforward: the CPU usage does not significantly change between epochs, and so we can request the appropriate amount by getting the CPU usage results from the first job.

For runtime, we decided to run the training script with the requirement that it complete at least fifty epochs but allow for early stopping after that point, if model accuracy failed to

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram of the flow of operations between eScriptorium instance, htr2hpc installation, and Slurm, including the two-job workflow of a preliminary calibration job before a second calibrated training job.

improve for ten epochs. This choice of fifty epochs was decided upon after conversations with other users of the Kraken ATR engine. (For handwritten manuscript material especially, other users generally agreed that without that minimum fifty epoch parameter set, the early stopping function of the engine was prone to ending the model training too early and with poor accuracy results.) We therefore calculated the requested runtime for the second job by using the setup time and average epoch runtime of the first job and assuming a total epoch count of fifty across both jobs. Following Research Computing suggestions, we then added a buffer of 10% additional time to allow for additional epochs if necessary and to guard against the actual runtime exceeding the requested limit.

Because our use case is a machine learning one where training runs over multiple epochs with intermediary models saved after each epoch, we do not need to start the second train job from scratch. Rather, we can set our script to continue the second train job from the last model saved from the first job: time and compute resources therefore are not wasted in our two-job model.

For some especially small training jobs (primarily during testing, but occasionally when a user is refining a model on only a few pages) the model training will already complete during the first Slurm job. Our code therefore checks the completion status of the first job before determining whether to run the second job.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The eScriptorium test instance described here, which we deployed and integrated with Princeton HPC resources, has been successfully used during a beta testing period by a mix

of faculty, graduate students, and staff who have used the software to run recognition tasks, create training data, and train new models. This period has already shown the range of ways members of the campus community interact with this kind of software: from those empowered by the GUI to run already-published HTR models on their manuscript images, to those importing large image corpora and refining their own models to tackle such material. Research projects from multiple academic departments – History, Religion, Near Eastern Studies, and Comparative Literature – took advantage of the infrastructure during the beta test. These applied the technology to a varied cross-section of cultural materials: nineteenth century German print, indigenous Mayan manuscripts, medieval Arabic manuscripts, and the handwriting of Sigmund Freud. The beta test concluded at the end of the summer and we are now sharing our findings from the testing and development phases to campus partners along with recommendations about what it would take to deploy and support a production instance of eScriptorium at Princeton. Our work has demonstrated the need and value of such a service, and also demonstrated one possible solution based on existing infrastructure.

It is not possible or appropriate for a small research unit like CDH to maintain and support a production institutional resource like this one. However, the work we have done here can lay the groundwork by providing information and specific recommendations to make it easier for institutional adoption at Princeton. While our work and immediate goals are primarily directed at our own context, we hope our work will also benefit other institutions with similar infrastructure and constraints who are interested in adopting eScriptorium. Even if our approach is not adopted entirely, parts of our solutions may well be adaptable and useful elsewhere, or even in different systems.

The solution we arrived at for our beta testing is not the only possible solution, but the lessons learned along the way provide a rich set of possibilities for future directions which we could have not discovered without this level of engagement with the technology.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Princeton Language and Intelligence (PLI) Seed Grant Program and a collaborative research grant from the Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton. We wish to thank Marina Rustow and Helmut Reimitz for their role in making this work possible as part of the “Princeton Open HTR Initiative.” We are additionally grateful for support and assistance provided by Princeton University Library IT and Princeton Research Computing.

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